

LEADERSHIP AS A TOOL FOR ORGANIZATIONAL SUCCESS: PROMOTING QUALITY SERVICE, INNOVATION, AND EXCELLENCE

¹Adamu Yusuf Ibrahim and ²Abubakar, Fatima Suleiman

¹Nasarawa State Polytechnic, Lafia, Nigeria

²Department of Hospitality Management, Abubakar Tatar Ali Polytechnic, Bauchi.

Abstract: Leadership is a vital element in the social relationship of group at work. Groups need leaders and leaders need followers. Leadership is a dynamic process influenced by the changing requirements of the task, the group itself and the individual members. Hospitality industry is a diverse and flexible sector that caters for eating, sleeping and recreational needs of all types and ages customers. Provision studies show many perspectives of promoting the quality service by some researchers while others protested that job standardization had preferably resulted it quality service delivery. This industry ranges from eatery to the largest luxury hotel, restaurant and as a service-oriented establishment, staff need to be trained from time to time on the importance of providing quality service. The study discussed the rationales for quality service delivery. Transformational, Transactional Leadership, Job standardization and quality service. Finally, recommendation was made that since the majority of employees in organizations are employed in groups of one kind or another, attention to team-roles, group working and/ or team development is a crucial activity for management.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, transactional leadership, Job standardization, the job characteristic model.

INTRODUCTION

Good service is a decisive factor for repurchase and recommendation of customers (Spreng, MacKenzie, & Olshavsky, 1996). Service provision is one of core products in hotel industry faced with competition, quality service becomes the main source of competitiveness in the hotel industry, two main strategies are fundamental guarantee for the invariable status, creating new and retaining existing customers. The previous study indicated that the cost of acquiring new customer is much greater than the cost of retaining them (Varsha, 2013; Raicheld, 1996; Reichel & Sasser, 1990). Therefore, keeping satisfied, repeat and loyal customers become the principle of a business (Kunton, 1988) advanced that competitive advantage of hotel industry is based on especially high-quality service in order to establish fine public praise (Kunton 1988) previous research show that

leadership is one of the keys to promote organizational performance (Victor, Maria & Leopoldo, 2014; Hannes, Michael, & Tony, 2012; Hui, Anne & Katherine, 2011). Not only the leaders is a policy-maker

who play a decisive role in resource of acquirement, development and deployment, but he also guarantee the resource utilized to the turn out in an organization (Zhu, Chew, & Spangler, 2005). Leaders can appear at any level of an institution and are not exclusive to management. Successful leaders do however; have one thing in common, Giri & Santra (2010). They influence those around them in order to reap maximum benefit from the organization's resources, including its most vital and expensive its people. Libraries for instance require leadership just like business, government and non-profit organizations. Whether a public, special or academic library, that library's leaders directly affect everything from patron experience to successfully executing state mission, including resource allocation, service offered and collection development strategies, Dixon & Hart. (2010). In fact, the influence of leaders and their effectiveness in moving people to a shared vision can directly shape the library's people, its material, how patrons use or interact with them and whether or not that experience is beneficial. With leadership potentially playing such a vital role in the success of information centers and patron experiences, it is useful to consider the different types of leaders and their potential impact on libraries as organizations. Adams & Adams, (2009).

Current leadership theories describe leaders based upon traits or how influence and power are used to achieve objective when using trait-based descriptions, leaders may be classified as autocratic, democratic, bureaucratic or charismatic. Of view leaders' hip from the perspective of the exchange of power and its utilization to secure outcome leader are situational, transaction or transformational. A point to note is that not all leaders are created equal and leadership quality may vary enormously across industries or simply within an organization. In addition, identifying an individual leader's style is central to evaluating leadership quality and effectiveness especially as it relates to organizational goals. Below is a brief examination of each common leadership style mentioned above and their potential impact on a group as well as their relative usefulness. Brow, (2009).

Transformational leadership, with characteristics of inspirational motivation, idealized influence, intellectual stimulation and individualized consolidation, has great influence on their subordinates (Bass & Bass 2008; Howell & Avolin, 1993). Transformational leaders not only provide their employees with a vision and transmit a common goal of importance of quality service, but also give them consideration and stimulate their capacity in work. That is to say, quality service is increased under transformational leadership. However, in the case for transformational leadership with characteristics of contingent reward, management-by-exception active (Bass & Bass 2008; Howell & Avolio, 1993) is to establish a rule of exchanging labour for rewards. Transactional leaders are given the power to evaluate their subordinates by performing certain task of quality service (Weichum, Irene & William, 2005). Therefore, quality service retains positive influence by both transformational and transactional leadership. Some researchers suggested that innovation *behaviour* directly led to quality service, while other researchers supported that standardization arouse awareness of customers to quality service. These two contradictions can be traced to the literatures of innovation behaviour of Burns and Stalker (1961) and scientific management of Taylor (1911). The formers hold that dealing with uncertainty requires employees sparking new ideas which may satisfy various demands of customer innovation behaviour bring out better quality service with touching movements. The latter believed that coping with complex task demands procedure which makes sure that efficiency and elimination of waste, standardization of work process. Uniformity of a task enables employees to have standard to follow and know how that they get rewards by completing their responsibilities. Job standardization

result in better service in uniformity. However, the leader of an organization may fall in a dilemma when he desires to take both advantages of innovation behaviour and job standardization (Gilson, Mathieu, Shalley & Ruddy, 2005). Transformational leaders use knowledge, expertise and vision to change those around them in a way that makes them follow with deeply embedded buy-in that remains even when the leader that created it is no longer on the scene. Transformational leaders represent the most valuable form of leadership service. Followers are given the chance to change transforms and, in the process, develop themselves as contributors. It is particularly suited for fast paced, change-laden environments that demand creative problem solving and customer's commitments. Isaksen, (2007).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Current leadership theories describe leaders based upon traits or how influence and power are used to achieve objectives. When using traits-based descriptions, leaders may be classified as autocratic, democratic, bureaucratic or charismatic of view leadership from the perspective of the exchange of power and its utilization to secure outcomes, leaders are situational, transactional or transformational as pointed out earlier in addition, identifying and individual leader's style is central to evaluating leadership quality and effectiveness especially as it relates to organizational goals. In previous studies in order to attain operating efficiency, two contrary points were mentioned supporting innovation behaviour and encouraging persistence of job standardization. Although innovation is considered as a key of productivity, complying with the successful standardized process is also welcome in organization. This seemed that organizations on this subject are at an opposite pole (Gilson et al 2005).

Generally speaking, innovation behaviour is concrete output and profit of inventive formation (Heunks, 1998). It is created in the process of work, developing diverse solution (Drazin, Glynn & Kazanjian, 1999). Each member in an organization is encouraged to devote himself into creative activities and to engage in inventive problem solving the study showed that it helps promote performance for employees to create the workplace with supporting their motivation behaviour (Gilson et al, 2015). And, the employee feedback and freely communicating style are positively related to quality service and customer satisfaction (Sparks, Brandley, & Callan, 1997).

Job standardization in order hand is defined that, a job has its standardize procedures whose purpose is to lessen multiplicity and improve efficiency. Job standardization set a procedure of service practice which is delivered to a customer during his visit. This standardized procedure is welcome in an organization due to coordination strategy for preventing the cost of misuse and work properly confirm, for job standardization is to avoid redundant and complex task (Gilson et al, 2005). In addition, quality service is unpredictable if there is no standardized service procedure in an organization (Bowie & Chang. 2005). Therefore, high job standardization creates a clear image ad process performance measurement (Hsieh & Hsieh, 2001). In comparison, in a highly competitive hotel industry, innovation behaviour provides variability to fit job calls, while job standardization ensures a high degree of uniformity in the standard of service.

THE EFFECTS OF LEADERSHIP STYLE ON QUALITY SERVICE, THE ROLE OF INNOVATION BEHAVIOUR AND JOB STANDARDIZATION.

Transformational leaders encourage subordinates to pursue common goals, missions and vision instead of seeking their personal interest, (Bass, 1985). Employee's performance effectiveness exceeds the expectation. Therefore, transformational leadership brings out group cohesiveness, commitment,

trust, incentive and performance. Employees confiding in their leaders are stimulated to put more attention on group and organization, so they try to ameliorate the situation to achieve the goal. Transformational leaders who set clear standard and goals lead their subordinates toward high performance (Hartog, Muije & Koopman, 1997). A transformational leader, who impels employees to meet job requirements, has them keep satisfaction and performance by providing incentive (Louise & Robert, 2007). A transformational leader expects employees to offer customized service and retain a long-term relationship as long as they are happy in their work. The incentive behaviour of transformational leadership affects quality service (Chang, 2006). In Chang's research to the customers in the hotel, they care more about quality service than convenient parking and accommodation costs (Chang, 2006).

Innovation, Deci (1975) indicated that intrinsic motivates which dominate role of intrinsic motivation play in an individual behaviour is decisive factor to creativity (Oldman & Cummings, 1996), and motivation composes individual innovation (Amabile, 1988). To an employee, the most important intrinsic motivation is the leader's support. Those employees perceive that innovation behaviour generating substantial risks are supported by supervisors, feed incentives and willing to show their creativity. During the service process, employees encountering problems would try to solve them by using their creative idea (Wong & Pang, 2003). According to Burns and Stalker theory of groups, Burns & Stalker (1961) posited that in mechanistic (hierarchical) organizations loyalty is to the concern and obedience is to supervisors. Employees therefore will look for appropriate opportunity to show their innovation behaviours during interaction with customers to satisfy them. Therefore, the more customized services are enhanced. In an organization, personnel utterly understand necessary of variability which brings new thinking (Barling, Loughlin & Kelloway, 2002).

However, Gresor (1989) argued that structural and definite practice is the best way to control quality and improve performance because symbolic and institutional character gives specific rules and standard operating procedure.

Standardization is highlight of workflow control (Smith, 1996). A standard procedure or guide book is given service personnel to maintain quality service (Hsieh & Hsieh, 2001). Therefore, we advise that transactional leaders have their staff provide quality service through job standardization and transformational leaders have their staff provide quality service through innovation behaviour. Also, brand positioning is required for market segmentation due to understanding demand of customers and estimating request of users (Juwaheer, 2004). On the basis of the job characteristics model, the characteristic of the job creates the psychological stages of employees, whose internally motivated behaviour develops high quality work performance (Hackman and Oldham, 1976). Therefore, in order to fit the exclusive quality service of international tourist hotels, the business strategy focus on individualized service. For fitting the quality of intimate service, it is essential for transformational leaders to help service staff develop creative ideas and search for new resource to realize innovative thought to accomplish their jobs by giving a common goal

CONCLUSION

In this theoretical research, the researcher shows that the relationship between transformational leadership and quality service is enriched through innovation behaviour in any organization, as well as the relationship between transactional leadership and quality service is enriched through job

standardization. Therefore, considering business strategies for promoting quality service, innovation behaviour should be applied in hotels for their cost consideration.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. In an organization where members are willing to explore new procedure and try new methods to reach a common goal should be encouraged and rewarded at the end of successful exercise.
- ii. A number of specific strategies for re-designing or enriching properties of jobs intended to, enhance communication of members, prompting their innovative thinking while on the job.
- iii. By giving proper resource, building an innovative organizational climate can produce expressing opinions among members and so, can supportive leaders.
- iv. To actually practice job standardization, service procedure can increase the overall efficiency as job standardization produces unified quality service and easily control service procedure, which becomes a routine process and offers customers orderly service.
- v. By proper task design, building a clear routines and procedures and managing services staff with clear regulations of reward and punishment condition, we can expect job standardization enhance quality service in hotels organization.

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